

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATIONAL CLASSES

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Abstract: This article gives information about pedagogical technologies and how to use them.

Key words: innovative, pedagogical technologies (modern teaching systems), technical means of teaching, technology.

It is known to all of us that the application of pedagogical technologies in the educational system and process is one of the urgent issues of the present time. The quality of the educational process depends on the coordinated use of the pedagogical and innovative technologies used in the lesson and the subject. Education and technology are closely related depends. Technology means the Greek word "tecne" - art and skill, "logos" - teaching, and it is a technical and is a systematic way of creating, applying and defining knowledge, taking into account human resources and their interaction. Any pedagogical technology should have a scientific basis, that is, a social, economic, pedagogical, psychological and philosophical basis. When this technology is used, under the spiritual and intellectual influence of the teacher, it is necessary to ensure that every student can use their full potential. The spiritual and moral environment in higher educational institutions should create an opportunity for the equal use of the personality of the pedagogue and the student.

In order for the effective effect of pedagogical technologies and the further increase of the quality of the lesson, the material and technical support should be at a high level, and the method of teaching the content of education should be interrelated with the personality of the teacher. Each lesson, topic, educational subject has its own technology, that is, pedagogical technology in the educational process is an individual process, which is directed to one goal based on the needs of the student, is a pedagogical process aimed at providing a pre-planned and guaranteed result.

Technical means of education - help to visually demonstrate the educational material, its systematic delivery, allow students to understand and remember the educational material. Examples of such tools can be: slide projector, overhead projector, blackboard-notebook, blackboard-stand,

Educational tools are auxiliary materials that increase the effectiveness of teaching and, at the same time, the visual presentation of educational material.

Educational aids - graphs, drawings, samples, handouts, etc.

Educational and methodological materials - educational materials, exercises to strengthen the acquired educational materials. These help to activate students' independent work (worksheet, notes, checklist, texts).

The selection and use of various types of educational tools that help to accelerate the learning activities of students depends on the following:

1. Setting the goal;
2. To the main source of knowledge;
3. To the method of education;
4. Newness and complexity of educational material;
5. To the educational opportunities of students.

Innovative technology - (innovation in English "innovate" means innovation, innovation, and technology in Greek "technos" - art, skill and "logos" - science) means a new approach to educational forms, methods and methods.

Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and activities of teachers and students.

The success of new innovative technologies in the educational process depends on the preliminary design of the entire educational process. Also, it is important to determine in advance the level of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by students. It also depends on the ability to predict the extent to which the goal and result should be achieved. The main part of the educational process should be spent on the process of self-management of students. Students at this stage turn to the source of additional information. This resource was created by the teacher and includes textbooks, manuals, workbooks, lectures, monographs, magazines, newspaper articles, and technical means of teaching, with which the student works on himself. In this case, the teacher allocates time according to the characteristics and complexity of the subject.

Such an approach not only increases students' interest and love for science and profession, but also creates a foundation for the formation of the worldview of each student, increasing the ability to create new ideas, and becoming a mature specialist in their profession.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED:

1. PEDAGOGS international research journal.
2. <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/5702/570272314022/html/>
3. https://www.shsconferences.org/articles/shsconf/pdf/2020/15/shsconf_ictp2020_00079.pdf
4. <https://econferences.ru/index.php/arims/article/download/2499/1519>

